

Organization of Project Based Learning within the Framework of a Person-Oriented Approach

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ABSTRACT

Project based learning is an innovative direction in the field of person-centered approach in teaching process. The article reflects the tasks that can and must be achieved using the project method and analyzes issues based on the process of organization of project based learning within the framework of a person-oriented approach. Views are presented on the conditions for the formation of knowledge through project activities. An approximate list of difficulties that students encounter during project activities is presented. The work also describes the stages of working with projects and provides specific examples applicable in teaching process.

Keywords: person-centered approach, project based learning, teaching process, project activity, knowledge.

INTRODUCTION

Practice shows that the use of the project method in language teaching process allows students to master new forms of organizing students' activities and significantly contributes to improving the quality of knowledge. In our lessons, we teach students to think independently, find and solve problems, using knowledge from different fields for this purpose, and develop the ability to establish cause-and-effect relationships. The presence of a problem that is significant in research and creative terms, requiring integrated knowledge, helps students not only to master the necessary material well, but also develops thinking, independence, cognitive and creative activity.

The main advantages of the project-based teaching method are as follows:

- relevance.

At the center of technology is the student, his active participation, which allows him to apply acquired knowledge, skills and abilities, as well as to obtain this knowledge independently;

- creation of a comfortable educational environment.

The degree of teacher-student, student-student cooperation becomes a factor in the development and self-determination of the individual;

- differentiated approach.

The student chooses the topic of the project, taking into account his interests and capabilities. This will allow the student to realize his creative potential. As a result, many problems of student-centered learning are solved;

- use of information technology;

- formation of research skills;

- motivating nature: the right to choose, the opportunity to control the process and collaborate with classmates - all this increases the motivation of learning.

DISCUSSIONS

Only properly organized work will have a positive impact on students, will contribute to the independent acquisition of knowledge and experience from direct communication with real life, developing their ability to work with constantly changing information, independence, critical thinking, and initiative. If a student constantly engages in project activities during his study years, then in real adult life he will be more adapted, will be able to plan his own activities, navigate in a variety of situations, work together with different people, that is, adapt to environmental conditions.

Project-based learning is a useful alternative to the classroom system, but it does not replace it. Experts from countries with extensive experience in project-based learning believe that the project should be used as a complement to other types of learning. And in this case, the teacher will only diversify the educational work, turning the educational process into productive creative work [6].

The purpose of the project activity is to understand and apply by students the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in independent practical activities; mastering the communicative approach as a universal algorithm of transformative and creative activity; development of intellectual potential and professional self-determination of students [5].

Expanding the ways of working with sources of information, increasing the independent role of students in project activities forms key, basic competencies: creation, search, collection, analysis, presentation, transmission of information, modeling (including computer), design, joint activities, reflection, self-study.

Project activities allow the teacher to organize work with different groups of students, which to a certain extent indicates the path of advancement of each student from a lower to a higher level of learning - from reproductive to creative.

When guiding students' project activities, an additional difficulty for the teacher is that there is no identical recipe that allows one to immediately give an unambiguous solution to various problems. Consulting in the process of working on projects requires the teacher to have broad erudition and high pedagogical skills, because Project topics range across a wide range of different areas of expertise.

A teacher's professionalism is expressed in how confidently he can plan students' work on a project, provides surprise and motivation for work, so that the task is not too easy, not too difficult, and is in the zone of proximal development of each student. The teacher's craft is to be able to control only the key moments (stages) of the project, working according to the method of decreasing hints, delegating the right to make decisions to the student [4]. Types of Projects Used in teaching process:

1. Creative. This type of project requires clear planning of the final results and the form of their presentation. The structure of the project is only outlined and further developed in the course of work, subject to the genre of the final result and

the interests of the participants, but already at the very beginning it is specified what the project will be.

2. Practice-oriented project (solving practical problems, conducting research);

3. Educational project (reproduction of any stages of research of technological objects)

4. Introductory and orientation (informational). It is expected that project participants will be familiarized with specific information, analyzed and summarized for a wide audience. Such projects are related to the use of ICT technologies, the creation of multimedia presentations and films.

5. Social projects (helping members of society - toys for orphans and disabled students, crafts, clean-up campaigns, promoting a healthy lifestyle, helping frequently ill groupmates) [4]

Regardless of the desire of the teacher, his beliefs, priorities, motivations and life concepts also participate in the process of transferring knowledge. This is where the problem of the need to develop the creative thinking of students arises and, as a prerequisite for implementing this in practice, the elimination of the dominant role of the teacher in the process of appropriating knowledge and experience.

The introduction of elements of student research activity into pedagogical technologies allows the teacher not only and not so much to teach, but to help the student learn and direct his cognitive activity. One of the most common types of research work among students in the learning process today is the project method.

The most difficult thing for a teacher during design is the role of an independent consultant. It is difficult to resist giving hints, especially if the teacher sees that students are doing something incorrectly. But it is important during consultations only to answer questions that students have. It is easier for the teacher to predict the difficulties that students may encounter and, at the

preparatory stage, to create cards, algorithms, and instructions that will guide the students' research work.

When completing a project, students experience their own specific falsehoods and overcome them, and this is one of the leading pedagogical goals of the project method.

When implementing projects, the role of the teacher changes qualitatively. It varies at different stages of design. At the preparatory stage, he motivates students and unites the goals of the project. When planning and searching, he observes and advises. When creating a product - recommends, advises. During the presentation, together with the expert commission, he analyzes and evaluates students' work. The teacher at all stages acts as a consultant and assistant, and the emphasis of teaching is not on the content of the teaching, but on the process of applying existing knowledge.

The role of students in learning is also changing: they are active participants in the process. Work group activities help them learn to work as a "team". At the same time, the formation of such constructive critical thinking occurs, which is difficult to teach in the usual "lesson" form of teaching. Students develop their own view of information, and the assessment form no longer applies: "this is true, but this is false." Students are free to choose methods and types of activities to achieve their goals; no one tells them how and what to do.

Even an unsuccessful project also has great positive pedagogical value. At the stage of self-analysis and then defense, the teacher and students analyze in great detail the logic chosen by the designers, the reasons for failures, the consequences of activities, etc. understanding mistakes creates motivation for repeated activity, forms personal interest in new knowledge, since it was unsuccessfully selected information that created the situation of "failure." Such reflection allows you to form an adequate assessment (self-esteem) of the world around you and yourself in this world.

An educational project is different from just a collectively prepared event or group work with the provision of visual aids, which demonstrates the main result of working on the project - an analysis of activities and a method for solving a problem.

There are various forms of presentation: defense of work at a scientific conference, literary lounge, performance, exhibition of works, concert, festival, etc.

At the last stages of design, both the student and the teacher analyze and evaluate the results of the activity, which are often identified only with the completed project.

In fact, there are at least two results when using the project method. The first (hidden) is the pedagogical effect of including students in the “acquisition of knowledge” and its logical application: the formation of personal qualities, motivation, reflection and self-esteem, the ability to make choices and comprehend both the consequences of this choice and the results of one’s own activities. It is this effective component that often remains outside the scope of the teacher’s attention, and only the project itself is presented for evaluation. Therefore, a novice design leader should write down short summaries based on the results of observations of students, this will allow him to be more objective during the defense itself. The second component of evaluating the result is the project itself. Moreover, it is not the volume of acquired information (what has been studied) that is assessed, but its application in activities (how it is applied) to achieve the goal.

CONCLUSIONS

Project based learning in education contributes to the formation of the most important personal characteristics: responsibility, dedication, flexibility, teamwork skills, delegation of responsibilities, and focus on results. It is also worth noting that students gain experience in collecting and analyzing information, organizing work, clearly formulating their thoughts, presenting and evaluating results, and

completing work on time. The maximum positive effect from project activities in student-oriented learning is achieved through personal orientation and individualization of the process. Thus, the teacher identifies project groups according to the level of knowledge, degree of proficiency in certain skills, readiness for independent creative, analytical, intellectual work, which allows students to carry out activities at their level and develop at a comfortable pace.

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